

An Analytical Study on Covid-19 and Indian Stock Market

Dr Sadhna Bagchi¹
Nishtha Sharma²

ITM University, India¹
Career Point University²

ABSTRACT

Purpose: The novel corona virus has led to unprecedented repercussions on daily life and the economy. This article analyses the effect of epidemic COVID 19 on investment behavior of investors while investing in stocks during this pandemic times. As during the pandemic market was volatile and investors were very skeptical about the market returns. **Research Design:** This study uses analytical methods to evaluate the effect of pandemic on investor's behavior. The data was collected from various secondary sources to understand the effect of COVID 19 investment trends of investors. **Findings:** The result shows that investors are now more inclined towards the options which can offer them liquidity with good significant returns as due to lockdown the economic activities had slowed down and impacted the pockets of the investors. Maximum investors were negatively affected due to the hit of the first wave with a return of the second wave as well as they were required to pay huge hospital bills. So this was one of the reasons that contributed towards change in behavior from moderate to risky. **Practical Implications:** With this analytical study the investors will be able to formulate the strategies to invest in the market and also give them the outlook of the volatility and the dynamism of the share market along with an option of liquidity and hassle-free investment. **Social Implications:** This study will encourage the new investors to understand the benefits of market returns and add on to the existing investors to analyze the market and have optimum returns from the market.

Keywords: Volatility, Investment behavior, Financial risk, Investment strategies, A trade-off

Correspondence to: Dr Sadhna Bagchi, Email: sadhnab@itmuniversity.org

Received: September 15, **Accepted:** October 15, **Published:** October 26, 2021

Citation: Bagchi, S., & Sharma, N. (2021). An Analytical Study on Covid-19 and Indian Stock Market. Capital Market and Financial Review, 1(1), 3- DOI:

Copyright: 2021 by the authors. Licensee KMF Publishers (www.kmf-publishers.com). This article is an open access article distributed under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

INTRODUCTION

The rapid spread of the unprecedented COVID-9 pandemic has put the world in jeopardy and changed

the global outlook unexpectedly. Initially, the SARS CoV 2 virus, which caused the COVID19 outbreak triggered in Wuhan city, Hubei province of China in

December 2019, and with time it spread all over the globe. This pandemic is not only a global health emergency but also a significant global economic downturn too. As many countries adopt strict quarantine policies to fight the unseen pandemic, their economic activities are suddenly shut down. Transports being limited and even restricted among countries have slowed down global economic activities. Most importantly, consumers and firms have prevented their usual consumption patterns due to the creation of panic among them and created market abnormality. Uncertainty and risk created due to this pandemic, causing significant economic impact all over the globe affecting both advanced and emerging economies such as the United States, Spain, Italy, Brazil, and India. In this context, the financial market has responded with dramatic movement and is adversely affected. Economic turmoil associated with COVID-19 has affected the financial market severely which includes both stock and bond markets.

Although there is limited current literature related to the impact of COVID19 on the financial market, the existing empirical studies have provided an exciting result. Baret et al. (2020), in their research on financial markets and banks, have found that there is a fall in the share of oil, equity, and bonds throughout the world as a result of the COVID19 pandemic. Social distancing measures adversely affected the productivity of the companies and brought about a decrease in revenue, higher operating cost, and also cash flow challenges to the companies. In Europe, the Financial Times Stock Exchange 100 index witnessed a sharp 1 day fall since 1987 (BBC News, 2020). Igwe (2020) is of the view that the shock from this pandemic can increase the volatility that can negatively affect the economic and financial system of every country. Most of the developed and developing countries' financial markets are adversely affected by this unexpected pandemic. The leading economy of the world, the US stock market hit the circuit breaker mechanism four times in 10 days in March 2020 (Zhang et al., 2020). The stock market of Europe and Asia has also jumped. The United Kingdom's leading index FTSE has fallen more than 10% on March 12, 2020 (Zhang et al., 2020). Vishnoi and Mookerjee (2020) observed that the stock market in Japan had dropped more than 20% in December 2019. The stock market of Spain, Hong Kong, and China also declined to 25.1, 14.75, and 12.1% in their price from March 8,

2020 to March 18, 2020 (Shehzad et al., 2020). In his study, also found a harmful impact of the COVID-19 on stock returns of the S&P 500 and an inconsequential impact on the Nasdaq composite index. Georgieva (2020) pointed out that the COVID-19 pandemic brought the entire globe near to financial crises more hazardous than Global Crises 2007–2008.

Gradually the worst effect of the pandemic spread to the emerging economy too. If we consider the financial market of the emerging economy a gloomy picture caught our eyes as this economy is the worst-hit by the collapse of oil prices. The outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic makes this picture more critical. The top leading emerging economies such as Brazil, Russia, and Mexico gradually moved toward hard mobility restrictions that will bring down the emerging economies to a recession of 1% in 2020 (Herfero,). In South Korea, the Coronavirus disease caused KOSPI to drop below 1,600 in their history after 10 years (So, 2020). In China, higher uncertainty due to COVID-19 results in greater volatility of stock return (Leduc & Liu, 2020). The government of India announced Janata Curfew on March 22, 2020 and a lockdown policy to maintain social distancing practices to slow down the outbreaks from March 24, 2020. As the government announced such a lockdown policy, various economic activities have been stopped suddenly. The financial market of India is witnessing sharp volatility as a result of the disruption of the global market (Raja Ram, 2020). As a result of the fallout in the global financial market, the Indian stock market also witnesses sharp volatility. It has also borne the brunt of the COVID-19 pandemic.

There are two major stock indices in India—Bombay Stock Exchange (BSE), Sensex, and National Stock Exchange (NSE), Nifty. If we look at the Bombay Stock Exchange there is a drop in the Sensex index to 13.2% on March 23, 2020. It was the highest single they fall after the news of the Harshad Mehta Scam, April 28, 1991 (Mandal, 2020). Similarly, Nifty has also declined to almost 29% during this period. Some economists have considered the impact of COVID19 on the Indian stock market as a “black swan event,” that is, the occurrence of a highly unanticipated event with an extremely bad impact. Due to the lockdown policy adopted by the government, the factories have reduced the size of their labor force as well as production level which disrupted the supply chain.

Again, because of the uncertainty prevailing among mankind, people also reduce their consumption habits leading to demand side shock. Studies have also found that the entire previous pandemic had affected only the demand chain. But this COVID19 pandemic has affected both the demand chain and supply chain.

Despite the several literature on the impact of COVID-19 on the stock market of the entire economy, there is limited study on it especially in the case of an emerging economy. To shed light on this aspect, this paper attempts to investigate the impact of COVID-19 on the two important stock markets of India. Glosten–Jagannathan–Runkle (GJR) generalized autoregressive conditional heteroscedasticity (GJR GARCH) model is used to make the study more significant in terms of volatility in stock index prices due to the outbreak of the pandemic and lockdown policy adopted by the Indian Government. Major findings of the study reveal the volatile nature of BSE Sensex and NSE Nifty, the two prominent stock markets of India.

Research Questions

- Do any change in investment behavior witnesses during pandemic?
- Was volatility of Stock market may affected due to pandemic?
- What is different factors influence investment behavior?
- What is impact of retail investors on stock market volatility?

Pandemic Precedence of the Indian Investors

Due to the uneven impact of pandemic on different sectors and categories of the society lead to difference in consumer prospective, the optimistic trend have emerged both in terms of consumption and investment patterns during the pandemic.

The work from home culture resulted in transformation of the consumer behavior, coupled with prioritizing personal and family health which facilitated increase in elective spending and saving money among Indian consumers. Also work from home and lockdown gave the opportunity to investors to analyse their investments and track them which

contributed to in-depth analysis of trading and exploring the new alternatives for creating liquid assets.

Many sectors were benefitted due to paradigm shift in consumer behavior such as pharmaceuticals, telecom, FMCG, Banking, financial services including insurance. This effected positively Indian indices which have recorded optimistic gains from the due to the negative corrections in market in March 2020.

Following the market sell-off, this broad-based equities rally drew in additional retail investors, who were attracted by favorable stock prices. Over the previous financial year, foreign portfolio investors (FPIs) invested Rs 2,74,034 crores in Indian stock markets, which, together with mutual fund inflows of Rs 96,000 crore, helped the Nifty and Sensex to trade well above their pre-pandemic levels and near all-time highs today. In fact, the Rs 9,182 crore SIP mutual fund inflows in March 2021 was the largest in the previous 12 months, indicating a decline in income uncertainty and restored investor optimism.

Apart from equities, a growing number of Indians are diversifying their portfolios to include real estate, debt, insurance products, and gold due to a variety of variables. A combination of decreased pricing in major markets, tax benefits granted by various state governments, and the follow-on effect of WFH culture, which has mandated separate quarters for both working members of a typical nuclear family, have encouraged real estate investments. Many first-time homebuyers are hurrying to close on their dream homes, as evidenced by the rise in sales. Housing loans are now available at rates as low as 6.75 percent, and some state governments are easing stamp duty for registrations.

Due to the cultural and social importance associated with the yellow metal, India has traditionally been a top consumer of actual gold. However, in the aftermath of the pandemic, Indian consumers are looking at alternative investments such as gold exchange traded funds, gold mutual funds, and sovereign gold bonds (SGBs) to take advantage of gold's relative price stability and long-term return potential. Due to the cultural and social importance associated with the yellow metal, India has traditionally been a top consumer of actual gold. However, in the aftermath of the pandemic, Indian

consumers are looking at alternative investments such as gold exchange traded funds, gold mutual funds, and sovereign gold bonds (SGBs) to take advantage of gold's relative price stability and long-term return potential.

According to surveys, more than 70% of Indians are now putting more attention on raising their debt and insurance allocations in order to protect themselves in the event of another pandemic or tragedy in the future. As a result, traditional instruments such as fixed deposits and Public Provident Fund (PPF) have seen an increase in capital allocation, while knowledgeable investors are actively investing in mutual fund debt schemes, which provide a larger return potential than an FD or PPF. Because of increased consumer awareness of the importance of insurance in the post-pandemic era, the general and life insurance sectors have benefited the most. In addition to traditional life and medical insurance products, consumers are also buying home insurance to protect their real estate investments. Both life and general insurance businesses appear to be prepared to benefit from this trend, and their insured bases are expected to grow significantly in the coming years.

Furthermore, as outlined in the Union Budget for 2021, the foreign investment limit in Indian insurance companies has been raised from 49% to 74%, allowing foreign insurance firms to bring in international best practises, technology, processes, and long-term resources to help make insurance more accessible to the masses.

Despite the crushing effects of the first statewide lockdown in March 2020, the Indian economy has recovered stronger than ever, with most high-frequency lead indicators of consumption and investment demand strengthening through the third quarter of fiscal year 2020-21. The low-interest environment has acted as a further stimulant for both private consumption and investment, encouraging more Indians to spend their excess cash in a variety of financial products and asset classes. India presents a potential structural development storey for the next few decades, with a wide representation of attractive and high-return sectors such as technology, healthcare, consumer, and banking on its indices. Long-term prospects for the Indian economy remain bright if inflationary pressures are contained and the

low-interest rate environment is maintained, and investors would do well to remain involved across the many financial markets accessible today

Objective of the study

- (1) Capture the behavior of NSE before and after impact of Covid 19
- (2) Analyze the co-movement of NSE during before and after Covid 19.
- (3) Examine both symmetric and asymmetric volatility of before and during and select the best suitable model to define this volatility

Stock Market Volatility

Stock market volatility refers to risk and uncertainty associated with movement of stock market indexes such as Nifty or Sensex. In finance volatility denoted as σ , when rapid change in price of stock in either positive or negative, is volatility. Volatility can measure in specific time frame with reference to historic prices of stock. Volatility of stock market can be accessed on the basis of past data and other is market price of traded security. There are various models of volatility models i.e. traditional estimators, extreme value estimators and conditional models. With advancement of research that the financial market volatility is time varying and having volatility clustering effect, conditional models came into picture, as unconditional models lost its relevance as compare to conditional models. One of the model that has the ability to model conditional volatility or variance after incorporating these characteristics is Generalized Autoregressive Conditional Heteroskedasticity (GARCH) which was proposed by Bollerslev (1986). heteroscedasticity (ARCH) that was given by Engle in 1982, it provides us more flexible approach to understand dynamic structure of conditional variance (Chou, 1988).

EGARCH was promulgated by Nelson in 1991, TGARCH was bring out by Zakoian in 1994, GJR-GARCH by Glosten, Jganathan and Runkle in 1993. The GARCH processes are generalized ARCH processes in the sense that the squared volatility is allowed to depend on previous squared volatilities, as well as previous squared values of the process.

SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW

Table I: Main Information

Time span	2003-2021
Sources (Journals, Books, etc)	136
Documents	297
Average years from publication	4.89
Average citations per documents	6.067

Table 1 showing study conducted on stock market volatility, it showing most of study conducted during

2003 to 2021, in total 433 works done at the rate of 4.89 publications per year.

Image 1: Most relevant Author worked for stock market volatility

Chou (1988), a study conducted in the US market for the period 1962 to 1985 for determination of volatility and risk aversion scenario with help of GARCH model. Uncertainty was there in 1974, that causes the markets to plunge causing increase in volatility by 26%. Lamoureux and Lastrapes (1990) in their study contributed to the empirical evidence in usage of ARCH to capture the heteroskedasticity in stock returns. Conclusions found to be valid in the cases of analyzed stocks and this study further paved the way for the employment of ARCH and GARCH models in studying behavior of asset prices.

Blair et al. (2002) made comparative study of the S & P100 index and all its elementary stocks by estimating ARCH and TARARCH Model, with conclusion that a

majority of stocks have larger volatility response for negative returns compare to positive returns. Deb et al. (2003) did predictive analysis for the monthly responses of market indices and its volatility for BSE and NSE volatility Indian capital markets using eight different univariate models. Out-of-sample forecasting performance of these models shows that GARCH (1, 1) model outperforms the other models.

Ng and McAleer (2004) used simple GARCH (1, 1) and TARARCH (1, 1) models for testing, estimation and forecasting the volatility of daily returns in S&P 500 Index and the Nikkei 225 Index. Their empirical results indicate that the forecasting performance of both models depends on the data set used. Karmakar (2005) used conditional volatility models to estimate

the volatility of 50 individual stocks of Indian stock exchange and observed that the GARCH (1, 1) model gives fairly good forecast. Pandey (2005) showed that extreme value estimators perform better than the conditional volatility models in the case of Indian stock market. Banerjee and Sarkar (2006) for Indian stock market, observed that the asymmetric GARCH models provide better fit than the symmetric GARCH model, confirming the presence of leverage effect. Magnus and Fosu (2006) estimated GARCH type models for daily returns of the Ghana Stock Exchange Market and found that the GARCH (1, 1) model outperforms.

Trilochan Tripathy & Luis Gil-Alana (2010) has examined the suitability of various volatility forecasting model for National Stock Exchange of India. The data included in the study were the daily closing, high, low and open values of the NSE returns from 2005 to 2008. The study consist five models which were Historical/Rolling Window Moving Average Estimator, Exponentially Weighted Moving Average (EWMA), GARCH models, Extreme Value Indicators (EVI) and Volatility Index (VIX). The model comparison was done on the basis of which models were explained the ex-post volatility well. The study was revealed that the GARCH and VIX models to be the best methods for volatility forecasting based on Wald's constant test. The study concluded that due to low frequency data extreme value models fail to forecast.

Emenike, Kalu O (2010), investigated the volatility of stock market returns in Nigeria using GARCH (1,1) and the GJR-GARCH (1,1) models. Volatility clustering, leptokurtosis and leverage effects were examined for the NSE returns series from January 1985, to December 2008. The results from GARCH (1,1) model show that volatility of stock returns is persistent in Nigeria. The result of GJR-GARCH (1,1) model shows the existence of leverage effects in Nigeria stock returns. Also, the shape parameter estimated from GED reveals evidence of leptokurtosis in the NSE returns distribution. Finally, volatility.

Aastha KHERA & Dr. Miklesh Prasad YADAV (2020), studied to examine and forecast the volatility of the stock exchanges of emerging countries. It is found that the volatility of every stock return can be forecasted. Both ARCH and GARCH terms are

significant in all the cases. Their sum of the coefficients are large enough to denote the persistence of the volatility. The overall persistency of shock is largest in China's stock return and lowest in case of Chile's stock exchange as their parameters sum is highest and lowest respectively. The sum of α_1 & α_2 is less than one ($\alpha_1 + \alpha_2 < 1$) implies the mean reverting GARCH model. Comparing the result of short run and long run shock persistency, it is found that long run shock is more persistent than short run as their α_2 is larger than α_1 .

Table 2: Most Relevant Country's Contribution

Country	No of documents published	Country	No of documents published
INDIA	404	AUSTRALIA	8
USA	24	MALAYSIA	6
FRANCE	14	BANGLADESH	5
UK	14	SAUDIARABIA	5
TUNISIA	11	BAHRAIN	4

Table 2 showing number of publication on the topic, India is contributed 404 document with maximum 939 citations. University of Delhi and Indian Institute of Management contributed most.

DATA COLLECTION AND RESEARCH METHOD

Data Collection: To study the effect of Covid-19 on market Volatility and its impact on NSE and BSE market, we taken data from website of National Stock Exchange and data taken from March 1 2019 to September 03, 2021, in total 618 observations. Data of Nifty and Sensex taken for trading days i.e Monday to Friday, effect of Saturday and Sunday seen on Monday when market open for trading.

Research Methods: To understand the effect of Covid-19 news and its reaction on Market Volatility, we taken data from March 1 2019, when everything was normal and market volatility can be seen due to others factors.

1. Volatility Clustering- Volatility cluster was checked by plotting graph of log value of Nifty value
2. Arch Effect in Data set – Arch Test conducted on data set
3. To stationary on data set Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test conducted and outcome is shown in data analysis section.

Augmented Dickey fuller test conducted to check the stationary of data set.

Pre Testing on Data Set

1. Volatility Clustering

Chart 1: Time period Taken from March 1, 2019 – September 3, 2021

Chart 2: Time period Taken from March 1, 2020 – September 3, 2021

Above graph plot showing number of cases of due to Covid-19 spotted and registered with respect to time period. When we coincide this two above plots we can see volatility clustering in Nifty data.

Hypothesis of Study

H0₁: Nifty has a unit root (Non-Stationary)

H1₁: Nifty has not unit root (Stationary)

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test

data: $rNifty = \text{diff}(\log(Nifty))$

Dickey-Fuller = -7.628, Lag order = 8, p-value = 0.01

alternative hypothesis: stationary

H0₂: Nifty has no Arch effect

H1₂: Nifty has Arch effect

ARCH LM-test; Null hypothesis: no ARCH effects

Chi-squared = 208.12, df = 12, p-value < 2.2e-16

GARCH Model - Conditional Variance Dynamics

Coefficient(s): a0 a1 b1
 01 5.276e-06 1.712e-01 8.054e-

GARCH Model : sGARCH(1,1)

Mean Model : ARFIMA(0,0,0) Distribution : normal

LogLikelihood : 1906.626 Information Criteria

Asymptotic Critical Values (10% 5% 1%)

Joint Statistic: 1.07 1.24 1.6 Individual Statistic: 0.35 0.47 0.75

RESEARCH FINDINGS

<p>Optimal Parameters</p> <p>Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(> t)</p> <p>mu 0.001039 0.000323 3.2204 0.00128</p> <p>omega 0.000005 0.000006 0.8057 0.42041</p> <p>alpha1 0.157673 0.029787 5.2933 0.00000</p> <p>beta1 0.817882 0.032386 25.2538 0.00000</p> <p>Mu-Overall Mean of series</p> <p>Omega - is Constant</p>	<p>Robust Standard Errors</p> <p>Estimate Std. Error t value Pr(> t)</p> <p>mu 0.001039 0.001110 0.93568 0.349438</p> <p>omega 0.000005 0.000034 0.14615 0.883800</p> <p>alpha1 0.157673 0.051647 3.05288 0.002267</p> <p>beta1 0.817882 0.247889 3.29939 0.000969</p>
<p>Weighted Ljung-Box Test on Standardized Residuals</p> <p>statistic p-value</p> <p>Lag[1] 0.6958 0.4042</p> <p>Lag[2*(p+q)+(p+q)-1][2] 0.6961 0.6083</p> <p>Lag[4*(p+q)+(p+q)-1][5] 2.9691 0.4127</p> <p>d.o.f=0</p> <p>H0: No serial correlation</p>	<p>Weighted Ljung-Box Test on Standardized Squared Residuals</p> <p>statistic p-value</p> <p>Lag[1] 0.2152 0.6427</p> <p>Lag[2*(p+q)+(p+q)-1][5] 0.5227 0.9541</p> <p>Lag[4*(p+q)+(p+q)-1][9] 1.1222 0.9806</p> <p>Degree of freedom =2</p>
<p>Weighted ARCH LM Tests</p> <p>Statistic Shape Scale P-Value</p> <p>ARCH Lag[3] 0.008068 0.500 2.000 0.9284</p> <p>ARCH Lag[5] 0.334684 1.440 1.667 0.9309</p> <p>ARCH Lag[7] 0.547849 2.315 1.543 0.9739</p>	<p>Nyblom stability test</p> <p>Joint Statistic: 1.2768</p> <p>Individual Statistics:</p> <p>mu 0.1658</p> <p>omega 0.2076</p> <p>alpha1 0.1156</p> <p>beta1 0.1082</p>
<p>Sign Bias Test</p> <p>t-value prob sig</p> <p>Sign Bias 1.9871 0.04736 **</p> <p>Negative Sign Bias 0.8685 0.38544</p> <p>Positive Sign Bias 0.7513 0.45278</p> <p>Joint Effect 4.0064 0.26077</p>	<p>Adjusted Pearson Goodness-of-Fit Test:</p> <p>group statistic p-value(g-1)</p> <p>1 20 45.10 0.0006628</p> <p>2 30 61.73 0.0003748</p> <p>3 40 67.51 0.0030907</p> <p>4 50 85.79 0.0009019</p> <p>Elapsed time : 1.062779</p>

Image1: Conditional SD graph

Standard Conditional Standard deviation Curve is time varying and its showing the variation in Nifty

data Cleary visible. News Impact Curve – It showing Symmetrical GARCH mode

Image 2: News Impact Curve

To check the Covid-19 effect Taken Covid-19 as Dummy Variable and regression analysis taken Nifty as dependent variable.

Null Hypothesis: LN_NIFTY has a unit root

Lag Length: 0 (Automatic - based on SIC, maxlag=17)

		t-Statistic	Prob.*
Augmented Dickey-Fuller test statistic		-23.31299	0.0000
Test critical values:	1% level	-3.444009	
	5% level	-2.867457	
	10% level	-2.569984	

Augmented Dickey-Fuller Test Equation

Dependent Variable: D(LN_NIFTY)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LN_NIFTY(-1)	-1.073102	0.046030	-23.31299	0.0000
C	-0.000925	0.000717	-1.289794	0.1978

*MacKinnon (1996) one-sided p-values.

Source: Collected from www.nseindia.com and computed using EViews

It is found from the analysis that the selected sample index has obtained high volatility -1.074027 (-1.073102 0.000925) during the study period. That is 106 percent of volatility exist in the selected sample index during

the study period. Hence the hypothesis “The Index price returns of sample indices are not volatile” is rejected.

Heteroskedasticity Test: ARCH				
F-statistic	83.83623	Prob. F(1,469)		0.0000
Obs*R-squared	71.42597	Prob. Chi-Square(1)		0.0000
Test Equation:				
Dependent Variable: RESID^2				
Method: Least Squares				
Included observations: 471 after adjustments				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	7.97E-07	2.12E-07	3.757102	0.0002
RESID^2(-1)	0.389450	0.042534	9.156212	0.0000
R-squared	0.151647	Mean dependent var		1.31E-06
Adjusted R-squared	0.149839	S.D. dependent var		4.82E-06
S.E. of regression	4.44E-06	Akaike info criterion		-21.80754
Sum squared resid	9.25E-09	Schwarz criterion		-21.78990
Log likelihood	5137.677	Hannan-Quinn criter.		-21.80060
F-statistic	83.83623	Durbin-Watson stat		1.909313
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

P value is less than 5% of value thus Covid 19 significantly affected volatility of trading in NSE and this impact was reflected in Nifty index.

FINDINGS OF STUDY

Graph chart of log return series of Nifty showing volatility clustering having fat tail with highly leptokurtic.

Augment dicker fuller test was applied to check and verify stationary or presence of unit root p value is less 0.05, null hypothesis was not accepted means series is stationary. Arch Test results showing p value is less than 0.05 thus null hypothesis was not accepted, means Nifty series had Arch effect.

To knowing the order of GARCH Model, its result shown that GARCH model of order (1,1) and symmetrical GARCH or standard GARCH estimated.

In GARCH Model- Alpha 1 and Beta 1 is positive, it was showing that if any news in the market is significant, means this news had significantly affected volatility.

Standard Conditional Standard deviation Curve is showing time varying and the variation in Nifty data, it was clearly visible in Curve. News impact curve depicting that what was news in the market it was captured and its showing symmetrical volatility, means its showing variation on both whether positive or negative news it was equally captured.

To check and verify the impact of news on Covid-19 and its impact on Nifty index, we were conducted regression analysis as taken number of Covid-19th cases registered as Dummy Variable and Nifty as dependent variable.

It is found from the analysis that the selected sample index has obtained high volatility -1.074027 (-1.073102 0.000925) during the study period. That is 106 percent of volatility exist in the selected sample index during the study period. Hence the hypothesis "The Index price returns of sample indices are not volatile" is rejected.

CONCLUSION

Stock market volatility refers to the risk and uncertainty associated with the movement of stock market indices such as nifty and stock market. Volatility can measure in specific time frame with reference to historic prices of stock. There are various models to study volatility of share market such as traditional estimators. To analyze the impact of Covid-19 and Indian stock market systematic literature review was also done as it was showing most of the study was done during 2003-2021 with total 433 works done at the rate of 4.89 publications

per year. Most Relevant Country's Contribution was from India where the major contribution was by Author S.Kumar. During the pandemic Indian investors were very optimistic as there was the transformation of the consumer to work from home culture and they were utilizing the time to analyze their investments. Due to a variety of factors, Indians are diversifying their portfolios to include real estate, debt, insurance products, and gold. To take advantage of gold's relative price stability and long-term return potential, Indian consumers are turning into alternative assets such as gold exchange traded funds, gold mutual funds, and sovereign gold bonds (SGBs).

Therefore the study was conducted to analyze the impact of COVID - 19 on Stock Market with specific reference to National Stock Exchange. Result from the GARCH (1, 1). The impact of COVID - 19 and higher amount of equities been sold significant impact on index in India. Hence with the results of all the analysis it can be understood that the COVID-19 in India made an adverse impact in automobile sector during the study period. The sudden fall of stock values affect the industry manufacturing process and it has been influenced the stock market for a period and it may recover soon with optimum potential.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, F., Syed, A. A., Kamal, M. A., López-garcía, M. de las N., Ramos-requena, J. P., & Gupta, S. (2021). Assessing the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on the stock and commodity markets performance and sustainability: A comparative analysis of South Asian countries. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 13(10). <https://doi.org/10.3390/su13105669>
- Baker, H. K., & Ricciardi, V. (2014). How Biases Affect Investor Behaviour. *The European Financial Review*, 7-10.
- Bhowmik, R., & Wang, S. (2020). *Stock Market Volatility and Return Analysis* : 1-18.
- Gurbaxani, A., & Gupte, R. (2021). A study on the impact of covid-19 on investor behaviour of individuals in a small town in the state of Madhya Pradesh, India. *Australasian Accounting, Business and Finance Journal*, 15(1 Special Issue), 70-92. <https://doi.org/10.14453/aabfj.v15i1.6>
- Jamous, R., Alrahhal, H., & El-Darieby, M. (2021). A New ANN-Particle Swarm Optimization with

- Center of Gravity (ANN-PSOCoG) Prediction Model for the Stock Market under the Effect of COVID-19. *Scientific Programming*, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2021/6656150>
- Mehta, S., & Nerlekar, V. (2020). Analytical study of the factors impacting the stock market volatility during CoVid-19. *Journal of Seybold Report*, 15(9), 3808–3826.
- Obamuyi, T. M. (2013). Factors Influencing Investment Decisions in Capital Market: a Study of Individual Investors in Nigeria. *Organizations and Markets in Emerging Economies*, 4(1), 141–161. <https://doi.org/10.15388/omee.2013.4.1.14263>
- Sharma, S., Aggarwal, V., & Yadav, M. P. (2020). Comparison of linear and non-linear GARCH models for forecasting volatility of select emerging countries. *Journal of Advances in Management Research*, December. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JAMR-07-2020-0152>
- Sharma, S. S. (2020). A Note on the Asian Market Volatility During the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Asian Economics Letters*, 1, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.46557/001c.17661>
- Talwar, M., Talwar, S., Kaur, P., Tripathy, N., & Dhir, A. (2021). Has financial attitude impacted the trading activity of retail investors during the COVID-19 pandemic? *Journal of Retailing and Consumer Services*, 58, 102341. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jretconser.2020.102341>
- Thomas, T. C., Sankararaman, G., & Suresh, S. (2020). Impact of Covid-19 Announcements on Nifty Stocks. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(14), 471–475. <https://doi.org/10.31838/jcr.07.14.124>
- Xiang, G., Second, G., General, P., Xiang, G., Xiang, G., He, K., Feng, Y., An, S., Xu, J., Liu, F., Ding, Q., Li, W., & Xia, Z. (2020). Preprint not peer reviewed. *BioRxiv*, 2(Iv).
- Yadav, M. (2020). Predicting the volatility in stock return of emerging economy: An empirical approach. *Theoretical and Applied Economics*, XXVII(4), 233–244
- Zali, M., Yudi Heryadi, A., Nurlaila, S., & Fanani, Z. (2018). International Journal of Advanced Multidisciplinary Research Madura cattle agribusiness performance and feasibility in Galis region, Madura. *Int. J. Adv. Multidiscip. Res*, 5(6), 45–55. <https://doi.org/10.22192/ijamr>
- Zhang, D., Hu, M., & Ji, Q. (2020). Financial markets under the global pandemic of COVID-19. *Finance Research Letters*, 36, 101528. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.frl.2020.101528>
- The outbreak of COVID-19 pandemic and its impact on stock market volatility: Evidence from a worst-affected economy, Debakshi Boral | Daisy Basistha, 7 January 2021
- Firzli, M. N. (2020). Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Financial_market_impact_of_the_COVID-19_pandemic.
- Igwe, P. A. (2020). Coronavirus with looming global health and economic doom. *African Development Institute of Research Methodology*, 1 (1), 1–6
- Raja Ram, A. (2020). COVID-19 and the stock market crash. *Outlook Money*. New Delhi, India: Outlook. <https://www.outlookindia.com/outlookmoney/mutual-funds/the-indian-investors-post-pandemic-precedence-7644>
- https://www1.nseindia.com/products/content/equities/indices/historical_index_data.htm
- <https://groww.in/p/volatility/>